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DESIGNING HOME USE MEDICAL DEVICES: THE CHALLENGES AND ITS REQUIREMENTS

Abdusselam Selami Cifter / Hua Dong / Julie Barnett,
Department of Industrial Product Design, Mimar Sinan Fine Arts University, Istanbul, Turkey /
School of Engineering and Design, Brunel University, Middlesex, UK /
Department of Information Systems and Computing, Brunel University, Middlesex, UK.
acifter@msgsu.edu.tr

ABSTRACT

An emerging trend of the healthcare industry is the huge increase in the number of medical devices being used by lay people at home. Although home healthcare is a fast growing field and home use medical devices are an emerging market, there is surprisingly little information readily available for designers. This paper particularly focuses on the design aspect of such devices. It investigates the design process of home use medical devices and the main challenges in designing such devices. It also presents designers' perspectives on designing home use medical devices. In order to understand the designers' requirements in designing home use medical devices, a questionnaire survey was carried out with professional designers. The results are presented and discussed in this paper. A design process model, called the 'Dual Verification Model' has been developed specifically for designing home use medical devices.

Keywords: Home use medical devices, design process, requirements

INTRODUCTION

Increasingly, medical devices are being used by lay people outside the clinical environment (FDA, 2010). Gossink & Souquet (2006) argue that, the e-health and personal healthcare is one of the major trends in healthcare technology. They also note that conventional interactions with patients are changing, and today patients take more responsibility of their own health. As a result, "many patients today seek to play an active role in prevention and medical treatment" (Klatzky & Ayoub, 1995). This emerging trend requires better understanding of user-product

interactions. It is expected that the home-healthcare market will grow continuously in the future (Ghandi, 2005). In the UK, the self-diagnostics market has been growing by 6% per year since 2002 from £71 million to £99 million in 2007, and more rapid growth is forecast to 2012 (Intel, 2007).

Many home-use medical devices are used by non-professional people who vary significantly in terms of their knowledge and capabilities (Gupta, 2007; Rogers et al, 2001; Wiklund & Wilcox, 2005). These people are frequently referred to as 'lay users'. For the purposes of this paper the definition of lay users was adapted from the European Standard BS EN ISO 18113-1:2009 (2009), where a lay person refers to: "an individual without formal training in a relevant medical field of discipline."

Lay users differ significantly from professional users and they vary in terms of their needs and capabilities (Kaye & Crowley, 2000, Wiklund & Wilcox, 2005). They may have various disabilities, chronic diseases and/or they may suffer from age-related capability deterioration (Kaye & Crowley, 2000; Sawyer, 1996; Wiklund & Wilcox, 2005). In particular, older people are one of the frequent users of home use medical devices. These people are likely to have at least one chronic disease and may need to use home-monitoring devices routinely due to their special conditions such as heart problems, diabetes, respiratory problems, etc (Lewis, 2001). If the products meet the needs and expectations of lay people, then home healthcare will "provide significant benefits to patients, in terms of both quality of life and cost of care" (FDA, 2010).

From 1997 to 2009 the FDA had received 19000 adverse event reports where the incident took place at home environments (FDA, 2010). Similarly, the Medicines and Healthcare products Regulatory Agency (MHRA) reported that they received 9099 adverse incidents in 2009 (MHRA, 2010), and the number of device reports by patients and professionals has risen over the past decade because of the complexity of the devices (MHRA, 2008); however, they did not mention the percentage of incidents that occurred in the home environment. These reports highlight the importance of the design aspect of such devices.

On the other hand designers are often accused of designing for themselves rather than for the actual users (Margolin, 1997; Keates & Clarkson, 2003; Keates & Clarkson, 2004; Wiklund & Wilcox, 2005). As suggested by Persad et al. (2007), during the early stages of the design process, designers require knowledge and data about the target users of the product in order to effectively evaluate its accessibility. Although home healthcare is a fast growing field and home use medical devices are an emerging market, there is surprisingly little information readily available for designers.

CHALLENGES OF DESIGNING HOME USE MEDICAL DEVICES

FDA (2010) identified three unique challenges for developing home use medical devices in their Medical Device Home Use Initiative:

Caregiver knowledge: Medical devices can be too complex for lay people to operate safely and effectively without training (FDA, 2010). This challenge was also mentioned by other researchers: Backinger & Kingsley (1993), Sawyer (1996), Kaye & Crowley (2000), Lewis (2001), Buckle et al. (2003), Patterson (2004), Fries (2006), Gupta (2007), BS EN ISO:14971 (2009a).

Device Usability: FDA (2010) divides this challenge into three aspects: (1) labelling and instructions, (2) individual needs of the users such as their capabilities or preferences, and (3) the obtaining of the device.

The information provided to the user with the device is critical (WHO, 2003). However this requirement is often poorly addressed by manufacturers, which results in problems with user-product interaction (Lewis, 2001; Patterson, 2004; Gupta, 2007; FDA, 2010). It is important to provide efficient labelling and instruction manuals in order to ensure safe use of home use medical devices.

Lay users vary significantly in terms of their needs and capabilities (Sawyer, 1996; Kaye & Crowley, 2000; Fries, 2001; Buckle, et al., 2003; Wiklund & Wilcox, 2005; Shah & Robinson, 2008). When designing medical devices for lay use, the characteristics of lay users should be taken into account (see Section 2.4). Generally “users appreciate medical devices that are easy to use, if they also know the devices are safe” (Kaye & Crowley, 2000: p.14).

Another important factor is, the way in which users obtain home use medical devices. In some cases these devices may be supplied to the patients by physicians. However, according to FDA (2010), generally physicians may not control which device is provided to the patient, because an equipment supplier provides these devices. They may prefer certain brands or models. Today many over-the-counter devices can be purchased via the Internet without the need for a prescription. Although Internet purchasing is advantageous in many ways, such as more control over purchases or lower prices, it still carries associated risks, e.g. the quality and reliability of the product (Meadows, 2005; MHRA, 2008; FDA, 2010).

Environmental Unpredictability: Home use medical devices are used in uncontrolled environments (Gupta, 2007; FDA, 2010). If the design of medical devices has problems, lay people can be easily confused during their interaction with the devices in the home environment (Lewis, 2001). Home environment can include risks which may affect the performance of the user or the product as well (Backinger & Kingsley, 1993; Lewis, 2001; FDA, 2010). Some of the environmental effects that may possibly affect the users are electromagnetic interference, noise levels, and the presence of household pets, etc (FDA, 2010).

Clarkson et al. (2004) argue that it is important that the designers and manufacturers of medical equipment take into account the various situations in which the products will be used; however, this is sometimes disregarded by designers. It is important to test medical devices in the intended environment of use (BSI, 2008).

DESIGN PROCESS OF HOME USE MEDICAL DEVICES

No literature was identified relating to the design process model specifically developed for home use medical devices. Home use medical devices are unique because despite the fact that these devices are used by lay people, they are medical devices which are complex and safety critical. As Gupta (2007) suggests, home use medical devices are everyday products but at the same time they are medical devices. Therefore two different design process approaches were investigated, i.e. the design process in general terms, and the design process for medical devices.

It has been found that there are a number of design process models, such as French's (1999) block diagram of design process, Pahl et al's (2007) design process model, Clarkson et al.'s (2007) waterfall model of an inclusive design process, Pugh's total design activity model (1991), and Stanton's (2004) user centred design process model. All these models are drawn as flow-diagrams. Generally in the design models there are feedback loops, which mean that iterative returns to earlier stages are possible, and in some cases necessary (Cross, 1996).

On the other hand, designing medical devices is a strict process. Medical devices must fulfil the regulatory requirements of the target market place and prove that they are developed in a way fitting with their purpose (Ward, et al., 2002).

Documentation of the verification and validation activities is part of this proof (BSI, 2003).

Verification is the activity to be performed "to ensure that the design and development outputs have met the design and development input requirements" (BSI, 2003: p.12). Ward et al. (2002) argue that, verification not only involves testing, but also other activities in order to provide evidence that

the necessary requirements are being met. On the other hand, validation is "to ensure that the resulting product is capable of meeting the requirements for the specified application or intended use", and this activity shall be completed before the product is delivered or implemented (BSI, 2003: p.12).

Verification and validation activities are found to be the most characteristic features of the medical device design process. During the literature review, two design process models were found that were specifically developed for medical device design: (1) Waterfall Design Process Model (FDA, 1997), and (2) Design for Validation (DFV) V-Model (Alexander, et al., 2001). Both models highlight the verification and validation activities in the medical device design processes.

On the other hand, Wiklund & Wilcox (2005) argues that developing medical devices for lay people requires a different approach from the ones designed for professional users. As more medical devices migrate into patients' homes, an inclusive design strategy becomes more important for making products usable (Wiklund & Wilcox, 2005). Owing to these issues, the design process of home use medical devices differs from both the processes for medical devices and for general consumer products.

INCLUSIVE DESIGN

The definition of inclusive design is adopted from the British Standards Institution: "design of mainstream products and/or services that are accessible to, and usable by, people with the widest range of abilities within the widest range of situations without the need for special adaptation or design" (BSI, 2005: p.8).

By means of inclusive design products can be designed in a way which can be accessible by people who are likely to be excluded by designers during the design process, i.e. older people and disabled people. However, inclusive design does not mean designing one product which can address the needs of the entire population (BSI, 2005; Clarkson, et al., 2007). According to Clarkson et al. (2007), inclusive design provides a better design by improving the product quality for a broad range of users. "By

determining the capability demand of a product on users, it is possible to identify and quantify those who have difficulty with, or cannot use it" (BSI, 2005: p.2), therefore knowing the needs of users is crucial.

DESIGNERS' REQUIREMENTS

Designers frequently use a variety of information sources in a wide range of formats, including their own experiences and imaginations (Goodman et al., 2007). However, as mentioned before, very little information is at the disposal of designers regarding the design of home use medical devices. Providing the necessary information for designers in a designer friendly way, may result in an effective and accurate management of the design process and may also help designers to design good devices which satisfy the needs and expectations of lay users. Therefore it is important to understand designers' perspectives and requirements when designing home use medical devices. For this purpose a questionnaire survey was carried out with professional designers.

STUDY METHOD

A structured self-administered online questionnaire, where the respondents filled in the questionnaire by themselves, was used (Robson, 2002). The questionnaire was prepared by means of the SurveyMonkey online survey tool.

The questionnaire included 10 questions and relevant questions were grouped into three sections in order to provide a logical flow: (1) The first section was prepared in order to collect general information about the participants, to see whether they matched the sampling criteria; (2) the second section focuses on understanding the designers' point of view in designing home use medical devices and their requirements regarding the design process, (3) the third section was about understanding the designers' requirements and preferences regarding a possible informational resource which might provide assistance to them when designing home use medical devices.

This paper focuses on the designers' perspectives and requirements, therefore the results relevant to these two criteria will be presented here.

SAMPLING

In order to recruit the participants purposive sampling (Robson, 2002) was utilised. The researcher wanted all the participants to be professional designers having a BA or BSc from a design related subject involving the design of products, and having at least 2 years of experience in the field. In order to approach possible respondents, personal contacts, Brunel University alumni, and other designers located in the UK were found through 'www.designdirectory.co.uk' and contacted. The questionnaire was sent to 400 designers and 53 of them responded.

ANALYSIS OF THE DATA

Two different methods were utilised when analysing the data, one for analysing answers to closed questions, and the other for answers to open-ended questions.

Coding was used to analyse the data collected via the open-ended questions (Robson, 2002). For the closed question, all the data was entered and analysed by means of SPSS statistical analysis software.

Two groups of designers were frequently compared during the analysis of the questions: (1) the designers who had prior experience in designing home use medical devices (n=18), and (2) the others with no experience (n=35). However, the numbers of the respondents were not equally distributed for the two groups. Also, because of small sample sizes, the data was not normally distributed. Owing to these issues, a non-parametric testing method, i.e. Mann-Whitney U test, was employed to undertake the statistical analysis (Field, 2005). Similarly when performing a Chi-Square test, the Exact significance value was considered due to small sample sizes (Field, 2005).

MAIN FINDINGS OF THE SURVEY

All the respondents had two or more years of design experience. 71.7% of the participants had 4 to 6 years of experience. 20.8% of the participants had more than 6 years of experience. The mean value is 5.6 years of experience. All the respondents hold a degree of a product design related subject.

DESIGNERS' POINTS OF VIEW REGARDING DESIGNING HOME USE MEDICAL DEVICES

The participants were asked if there was any difference in terms of the approach to the design of 'home use medical devices' when compared with 'everyday consumer products'. The results suggested that 76% of the participants think there is a difference. It was hypothesised that 'there would be a statistically significant association between prior experience in designing home use medical devices and the designers' thoughts on whether there was any difference in terms of the approach to designing home use medical devices when compared with everyday consumer products'. This was tested using a Pearson Chi-Square test.

According to the results no statistical significance was identified between the respondents with prior experience and the others without prior experience, where the p value was 0.470: ($\chi^2 (1) = 0.155$; $p > 0.05$).

The respondents were asked to indicate why they thought that there was a difference. In total, 87 reasons were given by the respondents. All these reasons were coded under 14 categories, including an "other" category. Figure 1 summarises the results.

Figure 1. The reasons indicated by the respondents.

Safety and risk of home use medical devices: As can be seen from Figure 1, 'Safety and the possible

risks of the device to the user' was the most mentioned category; it was mentioned by 16 designers. The respondents frequently mentioned that reliability of the product is a significant consideration with home use medical devices and incorrect action may pose a threat to the wellbeing of the user. These devices require extra attention so that they work accurately. It is also important that the devices do not lead to misuse.

User related issues: 'User related issues' were mentioned by 13 designers. The respondents mentioned that the diversity of the users and their capabilities should be taken into account during the design process of home use medical devices. Although the respondents frequently mentioned some of the lay user characteristics (e.g. the knowledge level of the participants, their capabilities or emotional needs) during this question, only one of these respondents used the term 'lay users'.

Regulations and Legislation: 'Regulations and legislation' was the third factor, mentioned by 12 respondents. They mentioned that the regulations are stricter for home use medical devices and due to the fact that these devices are accepted as medical devices, different types of standards are required. One of the respondents also mentioned that designers are concerned about their legal protection due to the possible risks to the users of the device.

Functionality and Usability: 10 respondents mentioned that there is more emphasis on the functionality and/or usability aspects of home use medical devices. In addition two respondents mentioned that functionality and usability were weighted more heavily in the design process than aesthetics.

Aesthetics Concerns: 5 respondents mentioned that home use medical devices require more attention to aesthetical considerations, as many existing medical devices feature a lack of any such styling. One participant mentioned that home use medical devices are special in that they have their own aesthetics which are associated with both clinical and consumer products.

Higher Cost of Development: 4 designers mentioned that home use medical devices often have higher cost of development, and consumers frequently find these devices expensive. In addition, higher costs of development sometimes affect the material selection or the manufacturing selection of the devices.

Material Selection: 4 respondents indicated that extra care should be given to material selection for home use medical devices, for example choosing body-safe materials.

Process is same but...: 4 respondents indicated that they think the process is similar but there are subtle differences in detail. They mentioned that the priority of the considerations and the requirements are different.

Longer Development Time: 2 respondents mentioned that home use medical devices have longer development time. One of these participants mentioned that this is the result of longer testing time for medical devices.

More Focus on Testing: 2 respondents mentioned that during the design and development process of home use medical devices there is more focus on user testing and product testing when compared with everyday consumer products, in order to make the medical device more robust.

Instructions are Critical: 2 respondents indicated that instruction manuals are critical for home use medical devices because usability of these devices frequently depends on the information provided in the manuals. Therefore the accompanying instructions should be easy to understand and easy to use.

Resistance to Changes: 2 respondents indicated that designers generally came up with the obvious solutions, because manufacturers are quite resistant to changes unless their advantages are justifiable. Manufacturers frequently look for high traceability.

Context of Use: 2 respondents mentioned that understanding the context of use is significant when designing home use medical devices.

DESIGNERS' REQUIREMENTS REGARDING DESIGNING HOME USE MEDICAL DEVICES

The designers were asked to scale four different types of information in terms of their importance throughout the design process of home use medical devices.

A five-point scale was used ('1': 'Not important'; '5': 'Very important'). An 'other' option was also provided. The overall results of the question can be seen in Figure 2 where the mean values are presented for each information type.

Figure 2. The mean values for four different types of information.

The overall score suggests that all of the four types of information are necessary during the design process of home use medical devices. The results suggest that the 'context of use of the product' and 'user information' have the highest importance (both with a mean value of 4.62).

In order to understand whether prior experience in designing home use medical devices had an effect on the designers' perspective, the results were assessed in order to identify any statistical significance. A Mann-Whitney U test was used for this purpose. A bonferroni correction was also applied to avoid the possibility of a type I error; therefore the critical value of .05 was divided by 4. The significance value for these tests was thus .013.

The results suggested that there are no significant differences between the designer groups to each of these information types.

The respondents were also asked to specify any other type of information requirement during the design process, and 8 designers responded, identifying 9 information types. These information types were further grouped into two categories:

- Current market information: 5 respondents mentioned that they require specific information about the current market, such as the information about similar products in the market, or the information about the current healthcare systems and any associated restrictions such as those on over-the-counter/prescriptive devices. One respondent also mentioned that market specific regulatory information would be useful, such as variation of regulations from region to region, or the recency of regulations for a specific market.
- Information from other stakeholders: 3 designers mentioned that they require direct information from other stakeholders involved in the process from the conception to production, such as medical doctors, nurses, patients, pharmacists, marketing organisations, manufacturers, regulatory bodies, etc.

THE INFORMATION SOURCES USED BY DESIGNERS

In order to understand what types of information sources are frequently used by designers during the design process, a multiple response question was prepared. A number of different types of information sources were given in order for the respondents to select the ones that they use regularly when designing products. In case respondents wished to identify other information sources that they use, an 'other' option was also provided.

The overall results of all the respondents were presented in Figure 3. According to the results, 90.6% of the respondents selected 'consulting a specialist', which suggests that it is the most used information source for all the designers. The second information source is 'observation' (selected by 88.7% of the respondents), and the third one is 'the internet' (selected by 81% of the respondents). On the other hand 'a toolkit' is the information source least used by designers. In fact, 3.8% of the respondents selected this option.

When designing a product, what source(s) do you generally use for collecting information? (If you have been involved in the design of a home-use medical device before, please answer this question based on that experience)

Figure 3. Information sources frequently used by designers.

Designers previously involved in home use medical device design were asked to respond to the question regarding their experience. It was hypothesised that 'designers use different types of information sources when designing a home use medical device'. For this purpose each of the information sources were tested separately by using a Pearson Chi-Square test. A bonferroni correction was applied, therefore the critical value of significance was .005 for these tests.

The results suggested no statistical significance for all the information sources.

The overall percentage of responses for each informational resource was also investigated for both designer groups (Figure 4). These information resources were gathered under two main categories, i.e. 'available information' and 'customised information'. Available information sources include: the Internet, books, intuition, academic journals, magazines and toolkits, where the information is often readily available. On the other hand customised information sources are derived from stakeholders where designers play an active role in the data collection or require interpreting the raw data in order to turn it into a design input; i.e. consulting a specialist, observation, interviews, by asking colleagues and conducting surveys. In this case designers require bespoke information for their specific project which is not readily available.

Figure 4. The overall percentage of responses for both available and customised information resources

The percentages suggested that except for ‘the internet’ (Figure 4), designers are less likely to use ‘available information’ sources (particularly ‘books’) when designing home use medical devices; and they are frequently more likely to use ‘customised information’.

10 designers also responded to the open-ended part of the question and identified 17 other information sources which were coded into 6 categories. Figure 5 shows these categories. The ‘other’ category includes all the other information sources which were mentioned by a single respondent.

Figure 5. Other information sources frequently used by designers.

The ‘other’ category includes 4 different types of information sources, i.e. ‘conferences’,

‘newspaper’, ‘academic research departments’, and ‘working as a diverse team’.

DISCUSSION

The results of the survey showed that the majority of the designers who took part in the survey think that there is a difference in terms of the approach to the design of home use medical devices when compared with everyday consumer products. The results also suggested that both the designers who had prior experience and the others having no experience responded similarly: both groups indicated that there should be a difference in terms of the approach. A number of reasons regarding the difference of the approach in designing a home use medical device were mentioned by the respondents. All the reasons were coded, and 13 categories were identified. The most frequently mentioned differences of home use medical devices were as follows:

Safety and risks of home use medical devices:

When designing home use medical devices, extra attention must be given to the safety of the device, because use errors may result in a risk to the health of users. The reliability and the accuracy of the device are significant and the design must help the user to use the device correctly.

User related issues: The users of home use medical devices vary significantly. During the design process, the characteristics of this diverse population must be taken into account. Users of home use medical devices may not have any training on how to use the device, and their knowledge level regarding their task might be very limited. In addition not only their physical requirements, but also emotional requirements must be addressed.

Regulations and legislation for home use medical devices: Regulations are strict for home use medical devices and different types of standards are required. When designing home use medical devices, designers must be aware of the regulatory framework of medical devices of the target market.

Functionality and usability of home use medical devices: Some of the respondents mentioned that functionality is more important when compared with aesthetics for home use medical devices. When

designing products designers should be more aware of the function of the device, and optimum usability must be ensured during the design process in order to prevent use errors.

It was also observed from the comments of the respondents that some of the reasons were associated with each other. For example:

The (1) manufacturers are resistant to changes because (2) the development costs of home use medical devices are high and (3) a new product development process is very long.

As can be seen from the above example where three different reasons mentioned by designers were interrelated, each of these factors form part of the process and one factor may link to another.

INFORMATION REQUIREMENT OF DESIGNERS

The survey showed that designers require different types of information when designing home use medical devices. Four different types of information (i.e. 'context of use', 'user information', 'regulations and legislation' and 'medical knowledge relevant to the design project') were given for the designers to rate. The results suggested that all these four information types are important during the design process; however, 'context of use' and 'user information' were rated as the most important ones. The respondents also suggested other information types, which were coded into two categories as 'current market information' and 'information from stakeholders'. Overall the study identified 6 types of designers' information requirements when designing home use medical devices.

Different types of informational resources were also investigated according to their frequency of use by designers, and the results showed that designers use a variety of informational resources. Overall the most used information resources included: (1) consulting a specialist, (2) observation and (3) the internet. Designers were less likely to use available information (e.g. books, magazines, academic journals, etc) when designing home use medical devices and they frequently use customised information (such as, interviews, observation, etc)

where they actively took part in the collection of the necessary information. Designers are less likely to use books when designing home use medical devices. This may be because of the lack of comprehensive books for designers to use during the design process of home use medical devices. They tend to adopt a more active approach in order to collect the necessary information. This suggests that there is a gap in this area, and providing information for designers for the design process of home use medical devices is necessary.

Similarly the results suggested that designers are less likely to seek information from their colleagues when designing home use medical devices. The reason may be that these devices are relatively new to the market and in essence they are medical devices. Therefore designers might prefer to collect the information personally from the stakeholders.

DESIGN PROCESS SUGGESTION FOR DESIGNING HOME USE MEDICAL DEVICES

Home use medical devices inherit the characteristics of both the design processes of everyday consumer products and medical devices (Gupta, 2007; Gardner-Bonneau, 2011). However, Wiklund & Wilcox (2005) suggest that these devices require a different approach than medical devices designed for professional use, because lay users differ significantly from professionals in terms of their needs and capabilities (Wiklund & Wilcox, 2005).

The results of the survey with designers also suggested that designing home use medical devices required a different approach during the design process, due to the inherently unique nature of the field.

In order to support designers during the design process, in particular those with no prior experience in designing home use medical devices, it was considered to be useful to outline the overall process and its associated requirements regarding the European market. However, as mentioned before, no literature was identified relating to the specific design process model for home use medical devices. On the other hand, a number of other models for both the design process in general terms and the design process for medical devices were identified.

On the basis of these models [in particular the Pahl et al's (2007) design process model, the waterfall model of an inclusive design process (Clarkson et al, 2007) and Waterfall Design Process Model (FDA, 1997)], a design process model was developed specifically for designers of home use medical devices, i.e. the 'Dual Verification Model for Designing Home Use Medical Devices' (Figure 6). The unique aspect of this model is that it highlights the understanding of both the regulatory requirements for the European market [derived from the Medical Devices Directive 93/42/EEC (MDD) and In Vitro Diagnostic Medical Devices Directive 98/79/EC (IVDMD)] and lay user requirements, and presents them as parallel tasks. In addition it also emphasises the verification and validation activities which are the important characteristics of the design process of medical devices.

Figure 6. Dual Verification Model for designing home use medical devices.

As can be seen in Figure 6, the model involves five main stages, i.e. discovering the needs, task clarification, design, testing and final validation. These stages are described below.

Discovering the Task

The process starts with a task and the desired outcomes of the task should be identified. Due to the fact that the design subject is a medical device which is used by lay users, two questions need to be answered: 'Who are the target lay users of the device?' and 'What is the intended purpose of the device?' According to the Directives, the 'intended purpose' of the device means "the use for which the device is intended..." (EEC, 1993; EC, 1998).

Task Clarification

In this stage the requirements of the task should be specified precisely in order to be used in the design stage. This stage involves two unique tasks which need to be carried out simultaneously as parallel tasks:

- The needs identified regarding the intended purpose of the device must be investigated through the 'Essential Requirements' of the relevant Directive (MDD or IVDMD) in order to prepare the documentation of the regulatory requirements.
- The requirements of the users should be investigated in accordance with the target lay users. This stage involves an intensive investigation of the user requirements which will result in the necessary documentation to ensure that the final product is designed inclusively and the capabilities of all the target lay users are taken into account. Emotional requirements of the users also should be considered during this activity.

Design

The design stage consists of two parts. In the first part requirements identified in the task clarification stage are translated into initial concepts. All the initial concepts should be verified with regard to the requirements.

In the second stage of the design process the best solution(s) is/are selected from within the concepts. It is important to verify that 'you are doing the thing right'. If the solution(s) selected is/are found to be unsuccessful, there is always an iteration loop to the prior design stage. The verification activity should be carried out during this stage and the necessary

documentation (for the Quality Systems requirements) should be prepared as the outcome of this activity (BSI, 2003). As a result, the best solution is selected and the prototype of the solution will be prepared for testing.

Testing

This stage involves the testing of the solution with real lay users. It is strongly recommended to test the prototype with different types of lay users and in the actual context in which the device will be used. There is an iteration loop to the design stage to improve the design. There is also a user feedback loop to the very beginning of the design process in order to check the requirements regarding the users and the intended purpose of the device if necessary. After all the improvements are made, the testing stage finishes.

In this stage, it should also be noted that a 'clinical evaluation' of the device might be required for the demonstration of the conformity with the relevant Directive. This may necessitate conducting clinical trials with ethical considerations in mind, in accordance with the mandatory Helsinki Declaration (EEC, 1993a).

Final Validation

As a final stage of the process, the validation activity is carried out prior to the production of the device in order to see whether the device meets the user needs; which helps to answer the question, 'have you built the right thing?' This activity must be documented to meet the Quality Systems requirements (BSI, 2003).

CONCLUSION

Designing home use medical devices is a unique process. Although these devices are, in fact, medical devices, they are used by lay people who may not have sufficient medical knowledge to operate them correctly. The context of use is also not clearly defined for home use medical devices. Therefore the safety and reliability of these devices is critical, especially as, in some cases, when lay users are dependent on these devices in order to sustain their wellbeing. This puts emphases on the functionality and usability of these devices in an effort to prevent

the errors in their use. However these devices still must meet the same regulatory requirements for medical devices for professionals' use. Owing to these issues, the design process of home use medical devices differs from both the processes for medical devices and for general consumer products. These factors bring additional challenges for designers during the design process, and therefore, when designing home use medical devices designers require an intensive process of collecting information. However, very limited information about home use medical devices is currently available for designers' use.

This paper presented the challenges in designing home use medical devices and designers' perspectives and requirements in designing such devices. A design process model (called the 'Dual Verification Model') specifically developed for home use medical devices, was also presented in this paper. The model is proposed to summarise the overall requirements for the design process of home use medical devices for the European market.

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